

Data set of measurement data vs test conditions for IT performance characterised in presence of separate and combined influence factors

Partner	INRIM
Measured power quality parameter	Amplitudes of the Harmonics
Influence factor 1	Adjacent phases
Influence factor 2 (if combined with 1)	Proximity
Index used to compare the reference power quality parameter with the measured power quality parameter	Harmonic ratio error defined as $\varepsilon_h = 100 \cdot \frac{k_n U_{s,h} - U_{p,h}}{U_{p,h}}$
Transducer under test	Capacitive LPVT: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rated primary voltage 20/√3 kV • Rated scale factor 20/√3 kV/V • Accuracy class 0.5
Measurement procedure (short description)	<p>A schematic representation of the adopted LPVT placement, aimed at assessing the effects of adjacent phases and proximity, is depicted in Figure 1.</p> <p align="center"><i>Fig 1: LPVT placement during experimental tests</i></p> <p>Three different tests are performed in order to assess the effect of separate influence factors (adjacent phases, proximity) and combined influence factors.</p> <p>A brief descriptions of the test procedure is provided below:</p> <p>-Adjacent phases: The three transducers (VT_A, VT_B and the LPVT under test) are supplied with three voltages (u_A, u_B and u_C) with the same amplitude level (20/√3 kV). The voltage signal provided to the LPVT under test is composed by the fundamental tone plus 1 harmonic tone (FH1) with amplitudes and frequencies listed in Table I. The two adjacent phases (u_A, u_B) are energized with sinusoidal voltages. The metallic plate is not included into the setup.</p> <p>-Proximity effect: The LPVT under test is supplied with FH1 test waveforms and the metallic plate is placed at 20 cm. The phases u_A and u_B are grounded.</p> <p>-Combined effect:</p>

The LPVT under test is supplied with FH1 test waveforms and a metallic plate is placed close to it (distance=20cm). The phases, u_A and u_B are energized as described in “Adjacent phases” section.

<i>Table I</i>	
h	$U_{C,h}$
2	2
3	5
5	6
7	5
17	2
25	2
50	0.5
82	0.5
115	0.5
148	0.5
180	0.5

The generation and measurement setup is represented in Figure 2.

Fig 2: Generation and measurement setup

Measurement Setup (short description)

The Low Voltage (LV) generation is achieved by synchronizing three Arbitrary Waveform Generators (AWGs). The MV signal supplied to the LPVT under test, is amplified using a voltage amplifier.

The two LV adjacent phases are amplified in two stages: first, they are amplified using two ± 150 V power amplifiers with variable gain, and then the signals are further amplified using two different step-up transformers.

To measure the MV test signal provided to the LPVT under test, a reference Resistive-Capacitive Voltage Divider (RCVD) is used.

For data acquisition, a compact DAQ chassis with multiple acquisition modules is employed. The system is used to acquire four different signals: the output of the RCVS, the LPVT output and the outputs of two VTs used to monitor the adjacent phases.

Main results (tables, plots,...)

Results of the test are provided in Figure 3 where three curves are reported. The blue curve is the harmonic ratio error response measured in presence of combined influence factors. The red curve refers to the case of adjacent phases energized. The black line is the harmonic ratio error measured in presence of the sole proximity effect.

Fig 3:CLPVT Results

References

Attached files

Name: 19NRM05_CLPVT_INRIM_Adjacent_Phases_Proximity.zip

Description: It contains 3 folders:

- one for the adjacent phases and proximity test (External_Position_Adjacent_Phases_Proximity);
- one for the proximity (External_Position_Proximity).
- one for the adjacent phases (External_Position_Adjacent_Phases).

Each folder includes files “.dat” corresponding to various measurement points listed in Table I.

The file name contains the following information:

“years_month_day_hour_minutes_seconds_fundamentalfrequency_fundamentalamplitude_harmonicorder_harmonicamplitude_harmonicphase”

example: “23_03_23_16_39_45_50_11547_3_5_0.dat”

Each file “.dat” includes the raw samples acquired for 1 s with a sampling frequency of $f_s=50$ kHz.

The raw samples acquired are:

1. RCVD output
2. CLPVT output
3. VT_A output
4. VT_B output

The Scale Factors to be used to refer all the measured secondary side data quantities to primary sides are:

1. 10182 V/V
2. 11547 V/V
3. 200 V/V
4. 346 V/V

Each file contains 50,000 columns and 4 row, elements of each row are separated by tab.

	<p>Example to read it: in Matlab environment:</p> <pre> folder='External_Position_Proximity'; %name of the folder file_list=dir([folder,'/*.dat']); nchan=4; SF=[10182,11547,200,346]; % scale factors fs=5e4; % sampling frequency for k=1:length(file_list) fid=fopen([file_list(k).folder,'/',file_list(k).name]); A=fread(fid,'double','ieee-le'); A=SF.*reshape(A,nchan, []); fclose(fid); *code for analysis* end </pre> <p>in this way A is composed of 4 rows, each row represents xx m of the acquired data referred to the primary side.</p>
<p>Agree to make the data public ? (yes/no)</p>	<p>yes</p>